

IMPLEMENTATION OF REGENT REGULATION NUMBER 72 OF 2022 CONCERNING LEBAK LEBUNG AUCTION PROCEDURES IN MUSI BANYUASIN REGENCY

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Abstract

The general lebak lebung auction is an area consisting of lebak, lebung, rivers and nyurung land (the term ex marga nyurung land is land that comes from/because of mud) which is naturally in the deep water season and a breeding ground for fish or other biota. This paper aims to describe and analyze the implementation of policies on the procedures for implementing lebak lebung auctions in 4 sub-districts in Sekayu District, Musi Banyuasin Regency. The research method used in this study is descriptive qualitative. The results of this study are that the implementation of policies on the procedures for implementing Lebak Lebung auctions in 4 sub-districts in Sekayu District has not been optimal due to the ineffective communication of policy makers and implementers, the low quality of human resources implementing the policy, and conflicts between farmers and land owners around Lebak Lebung and Rivers. To overcome these obstacles, the Regional Government is expected to better supervise the management of objects and improve coordination between Policy auction makers and implementers.

Keywords: *Lebak lebung auction, policy implementation, pengemin*

INTRODUCTION

Based on the Regulation of the Regent of Musi Banyuasin Number 72 of 2022 concerning Procedures for Implementing the Lebak Lebung Auction in Villages/Sub-districts in Musi Banyuasin Regency in Article 1, lebak is land that is inundated by water during the rainy season (floods) and dry during the dry season and is a fishing area and as a business area (other uses). Lebung is a depression or deep part found in the lebak, not dry during the dry season (although during the long dry season it will dry) and a place where fish gather when the water recedes. As well as the general lebak lebung auction is an area consisting of lebak, lebung, rivers and nyurung land (the term ex marga nyurung land is land that comes from/due to the presence of mud) which is naturally in the deep water season and a breeding ground for fish or other biota. In line with Article 6 paragraph (3) of the Regent's Regulation, the Head of Sekayu District requested that the 4 sub-districts in the Sekayu District area combine the implementation of the lebak lebung auction and host the auction implementation alternately every year in the 4 sub-districts, namely Soak Baru, Balai Agung, Serasan Jaya and Kayuara. The implementation of the lebak lebung auction can be seen in table 1.1 below.

Table 1. Lebak Lebung Auction Implementers in 4 Sub-districts in Sekayu District

No.	Year	Executor
1	2022	Balai Agung Subdistrict
2	2023	Serasan Jaya Village
3	2024	Soak Baru Village

Source: Sekayu District Activity Report 2022-2024

This aims to increase the efficiency of auction implementation and make it easier to report activities to the sub-district.1 There were 56 auction objects in the Lebak Lebung area of Soak Baru Village, Balai Agung, Serasan Jaya, Kayuara. The number of auction objects sold and unsold in 2022–2024 can be seen in Table 1.2 below.

Table 2. Data on Sold and Unsold Lebak Lebung Auction Objects in 2022-2024

No.	Year	Number of Auction Objects in Lebak Lebung		
		Sold	Not sold	Postponed
1	2022	45	9	2
2	2023	39	15	2
3	2024	41	13	2

Source: Sekayu District Activity Report 2022-2024

Based on the table above, the number of auction objects sold in 2024 for the 2025 period was 43 objects with 11 unsold objects and 2 auction objects postponed based on the Regent's Decree. Music Banyuasin No.140/119/101/1998. In addition, there is 6 Lebak Lebung auction objects that were not sold consecutively in 2022 – 2024 due to lack of interest and the silting of the river so that Lebak Lebung and the river no longer flow with water either in the dry or rainy season. Based on Article 2 paragraph (2) of the Regent's Regulation, the implementation of the lebak lebung auction is one of the sources of original village/sub-district income, but the disbursement of the lebak lebung auction results in 2022 and 2023 was carried out in 2024.3 The delay in disbursement resulted in the utilization of the lebak lebung auction results and the operational payments for the auction implementation being delayed for several years. This is due to the shift in policy that regulated the implementation of the lebak lebung auction, which was previously Regional Regulation Number 18 of 2005 concerning the Lebak Lebung and River Auction in Musi Banyuasin Regency which was revoked through Regional Regulation Number 3 of 2022 concerning the Revocation of Regional Regulation Number 18 of 2005 concerning the Lebak Lebung and River Auction in Musi Banyuasin Regency. One of the regulations that changed from the regulation to the Musi Banyuasin Regent Regulation Number 72 of 2022 concerning Procedures for Implementing Lebak Lebung Auctions in Villages/Sub-districts in Musi Banyuasin Regency is financial administration where previously the distribution of auction results could be carried out directly in the current year, whereas in the latest Regent Regulation, the distribution of auction results is carried out in the following year.

There are several previous studies related to the lebak lebung auction, including a journal by Maghfiroh Yenny (2022) which examines the form and content of the lebak lebung auction system policy in Ogan Ilir Regency, with the research results that the pengmin as the power holder in taking advantage of an auction object. Then there is also a journal by Radityo Pramoda (2011) which examines the Implementation of OKI Regional Regulation No. 9 of 2008 regarding the Management of Inland Public Waters from a legal perspective. And there are still several journals studying the lebak lebung auction through different scientific fields, including economics, sociology, and ecology or the environment. However, the fundamental difference between this research and previous research is that the author has not found research with a locus in Musi Banyuasin Regency and there are several different regulations between the Regent's Regulation in Muba and other regions regarding the lebak lebung auction, especially the distribution of auction proceeds and the value of the offer. These issues prompted the author to conduct this research. This study aims to determine the implementation of the lebak lebung auction policy in the four sub-districts and the influencing factors.

LITERATURE REVIEW

1. Public Policy

According to Aminullah (in Sore, BU, and Sobirin, 2017:2), the definition of policy is an effort or action to influence the system to achieve the desired goals. The efforts and actions in question are strategic, meaning long-term and comprehensive. Meanwhile, the public sector, according to Mardiasmo (in Firdausijah, RT, et al., 2023:5), is an entity whose activities are related to efforts to produce public goods and services in order to fulfill public needs and rights. The public sector includes services such as the police, military, highways, and health services for the poor. In relation to the understanding of policy and the public above, according to Riant Nugroho ((in Sore, BU and Sobirin, 2017:8) that public policy is referred to as public policy which means a rule that regulates communal life that must be obeyed and is binding on all citizens. In other words, policy is also a law where every violation will be given a sanction according to the weight of the violation committed and the sanction is imposed in front of the community by an institution that has the task of giving the sanction.

In addition, Thomas R. dye (in Sore, BU and Sobirin, 2017:9) also explains that public policy is everything that the government does, why they do it, and the results that create a shared life (whatever governments choose to do or not to do). Based on the various definitions of public policy above, public policy can be defined as government efforts and actions to address common problems in society and is binding. Furthermore, in preparing this paper, it is important to understand the policy implementation theory that will be used in its preparation.

2. Policy Implementation

According to Grindle (in Sobirin, 2023: 36), implementation is a general process of administrative action that can be studied at a specific program level. The implementation process begins after the determination of goals and objectives, the preparation of program activities, funding availability, and fund distribution to achieve targets. Furthermore, Van Meter and Van Horn (in Sobirin, 2023: 36) define policy implementation as actions taken by government and private organizations, both individually and in groups, to achieve objectives. Regarding the definition of policy implementation, Thomas B. Smith (1973) explains that in policy implementation, there are four variables that influence each other and have a reciprocal relationship. These four variables are as follows: 4

1. Idealized Policy

Idealized policies are defined as ideal interaction patterns that have been defined in the policy. will induced. Accurate and consistent communication and coordination with policy implementers is crucial. prospects for effective policy implementation. In the ideal policy there are 4 (four) categories of variables, namely:

- Formal policy is a form of policy in the form of a formal decision statement, law or program that the government wants to implement.
- Types of policies consist of 3 categories, namely:
 - a. Policies that are complex, broad and not gradual or simple with small-scale stages.
 - b. Policies in the organizational category that require modification/formation of formal or non-organizational organizations by forming interaction patterns outside formal organizational context.
 - c. Policy which are classified as distributive, redistributive, regulatory, self-regulatory, or emotive-symbolic.
- The program has the following aspects:
 - a. Intensity of support is the level of government commitment to policy implementation.
 - b. Policy sources are seen from the support and demands for a policy to meet the needs and demands of society.
 - c. Coverage is the extent of the policy, whether universal or concentrated in a particular geographic area. – The image of the policy created by the policy in society.

2. Target Groups

Target groups are groups directly affected by the policy and must adopt the interaction patterns expected by the policy formulation. Target group compliance depends on the suitability of the policy content to their expectations and communication between the implementer and the policy recipients. The communication process is influenced by the characteristics of each target group, such as education level, gender, age, experience, and socioeconomic status. This communication process greatly influences the effectiveness of policy implementation. In addition, there are several factors relevant to target groups, namely:

- a. Level of Organization or institutionalization of the target group.
- b. Leadership of target groups that support or oppose policies.
- c. Previous policy experience of the target group.

3. Implementing Organizations

are the implementing agencies or government bureaucratic units responsible for implementing the policy. There are 3 (three) variables that need to be considered. Considered in policy implementation, namely:

- a. Structure and personnel – stability of the qualification structure and personnel that must be implemented.
- b. Administrative organizational leadership, like target group leadership, refers to the style and nature of leadership.
- c. Program and implementation capacity refers to the attention to managing implementation and the general capacity of the organization to meet program implementation objectives.

4. Environmental Factors: Environmental elements that influence or are influenced by policy implementation, such as cultural, social, economic, and political aspects. In addition to policy, implementation theory deepens understanding of the topics discussed in this paper, so it is important to understand the meaning and definition of the Lebak Lebung auction concept.

3. Lebak Lebung Auction

Lebak Lebung is a term used by the people of South Sumatra to refer to seasonally inundated waters or flooded swamps. Scientifically, Lebak Lebung swamp waters are floodplain waters, which are lowlands along the banks of rivers that are inundated when the river overflows (during the rainy season). 5 Lebung is the deepest, trough-like part of the lebak/swamp, which is the headwaters of the river. As the low tide approaches, an auction is held that is open to all. 1 The lebak lebung auctioned refers to parts of the river and lowland with predetermined boundaries. The auction winners, called penguin, have the right to harvest fish and other products within the designated river sections. The fish in these areas are wild and not farmed. 6 Lebak Lebung auctions are one of the economic systems of the people of South Sumatra Province. This tradition has been going on since the time of the Palembang Kingdom (1587-1659) until today. During the Palembang Kingdom, this system was regulated in the Simbur Cahaya Law Book. Furthermore, during the colonial period (1821-1942), the Dutch changed several rules in Simbur Cahaya and regulated the auction proceeds distribution system. Then, auctions were conducted by the clan (the traditional community government group) (valid until 1982). During that period, the auction proceeds went to the clan's treasury. Currently, each region establishes regional regulations governing lebak lebung auctions and the distribution of auction proceeds between village/sub-district, sub-district, and district governments.7

METHOD

The writing design of this research is descriptive qualitative with data analysis using an inductive approach because in writing the author focuses more on describing or describing events that occur in the field systematically, logically and objectively, really existing in order to be able to understand every fact that occurs and solve existing problems using scientific methods. Data collection techniques [in this research include interviews, observation and documentation. The parties interviewed include the Head of Soak Baru Village, pengmin, and Soak Baru Village staff. Observations were made on the implementation of the Lebak Lebung auction in December 2024. Documentation includes collecting documents, reports, and photos of the implementation of the Lebak Lebung auction.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Implementation of the Policy on Procedures for the Lebak Lebung Auction in 4 Sub-districts in Sekayu District, Musi Banyuasin Regency in 2024

This research uses the policy implementation theory put forward by Thomas B. Smith (1973) with 4 dimensions, namely:

- a. Idealized policy;
- b. Target Group;
- c. Implementing Organization; and
- d. Environmental Factors.

Regarding policy implementation, the author will discuss these four dimensions to deepen the discussion regarding the implementation of the lebak lebung auction in 4 sub-districts in Sekayu District, which can be seen as follows.

a) Idealized Policy

As previously stated, according to Smith (1973), idealized policy can be seen from the ideal interaction patterns defined by the policy-implementing bureaucrats who are attempting to instill them. This communication is a difficult and complex process due to frequent intentional and unintentional disruptions within and outside the organization. Based on this dimension, accurate and consistent communication by policy implementers is crucial for effective policy implementation. The results of an interview with the Head of Soak Baru Village revealed that the implementation of the lebak lebung auction alternately by 4 Villages and the change in the position of the State Civil Apparatus (ASN) affected the success of the lebak lebung

auction. In 2024, Soak Baru Village became the organizer of the lebak lebung auction from 4 villages with the Head of the Village and the Head of the Government Section who were in charge for the first time, causing the need for more intense communication and coordination with other Village and District Governments. Meetings with the three other Village Heads to prepare for the lebak lebung auction itself have been held 3 times, but it is recognized that in the implementation there are still limitations. In addition, communication and coordination that has been carried out by the four Village Governments based on the archive of meeting minutes on November 6, 2024 at the Soak Baru Village Office that the meeting discussion included determining the proposed date for the auction, drafting a Joint Decree of the Village Heads of Soak Baru, Balai Agung, Serasan Jaya and Kayuara regarding the implementing committee, the number of objects for the lebak lebung auction, determining the host, and the series of events. Coordination between the four village heads has been effective, especially in preparing for the implementation of the lebak lebung auction. However, communication with other related parties such as the Sekayu District Government and the Community and Village Empowerment Service (DPMD) of Musi Banyuasin Regency, the Regional Financial and Asset Management Agency (BPKAD) of Musi Banyuasin Regency, and the Regional Tax and Retribution Management Agency (BPPRD) of Musi Banyuasin Regency regarding the implementation of the lebak lebung auction is still ineffective which causes problems in financial administration and utilization of the results of this auction.

The inaccuracy of communication is evident from the 2024 Soak Baru Village financial report that the income and disbursement of the 2022 and 2023 lebak lebung auction results can only be implemented in 2024. Based on this data, it is known that the implementation of the 2022 lebung auction was delayed for 1 year which caused the host organizer, namely the Balai Agung Village Government, to cover the implementation costs of 15% of the total auction results using the village head's personal expenses or debt to third parties. Based on the 2024 Sekayu District Activity Report, this delay was caused by a lack of coordination and communication between the DPMD of Musi Banyuasin Regency as the leading sector with other stakeholders, namely the BPKAD and BPPRD of Musi Banyuasin Regency regarding the financial administration of auction results in accordance with the Musi Banyuasin Regent Regulation Number 72 of 2022 concerning Procedures for Implementing Lebak Lebung Auctions in Villages/Sub-districts in Musi Banyuasin Regency.

b) Target Group

According to Smith (1973), the target group is a group that is directly affected by the policy and must adopt the interaction patterns expected by the policy formulation and the compliance of the target group depends on the suitability of the policy content with their expectations and communication between the policy implementers and the policy recipients. The target group in this study is the entire community in the Musi Banyuasin Regency area, specifically the community who is interested in participating in this lebak lebung auction. Based on the author's observations, the policy content that is the community's hope is certainly the policy's bias towards the community, such as the tax object's selling value that is not too high and in accordance with the fish catch in a year of lebak lebung management. In this regard, based on the report on the implementation of the lebak lebung auction that was carried out on December 2, 2024 at the Soak Baru Village Hall, there were 2 auction objects that were not sold because the initial offer in accordance with Article 7 of the Musi Banyuasin Regent Regulation Number 72 of 2022 concerning Procedures for Implementing Lebak Lebung Auctions in Villages/Sub-districts in Musi Banyuasin Regency, namely 75% of the previous year's selling price, which was too high. The auction objects in question are the Singat River, which in 2023 was sold for Rp 41,000,000 with a starting bid of Rp 30,750,000, and the Pinang Buring Lamban Kandis River, which was sold in 2023 for Rp 10,000,000 with a starting bid of Rp 7,000,000. As previously stated, based on the statement of the owner of both rivers in 2023, namely Mr. Edi Iduar, that their catch in that period was only enough to pay for the capital. This certainly became a benchmark for other communities so that the river was not sold or was considered dead on the auction table. To anticipate this, an offer was made outside the auction event by the Village Government to the community who were interested in buying fish at a selling price far below the starting offer. In addition, based on the author's observations during the implementation of the Lebak Lebung auction, there was also cooperation between several bidders to not take the auction objects they intended to take, resulting in several auction objects that had the potential to produce large fish and other biota but were sold at prices below 75% of the 2023 selling price. In addition, there are indeed several rivers that experienced a reduction in catch. As a result of these two things, there were several auction objects that experienced a decrease in price, some

even sold below the initial offer according to Article 7 of this Regent's Regulation as can be seen in the following table:

Table 3. Comparison of the Sales Value of Auction Objects in the Sub-districts of Soak Baru, Balai Agung, Serasan Jaya and Kayuara which Have Experienced a Decrease

No.	Auction Object Name	2023 Selling Price	Selling Price in 2024
1.	River Lake Barung	Rp. 4,000,000	Rp. 3,600,000
2.	Langgaran River	Rp. 26,000,000	Rp. 25,000,000
3.	River Seriously	Rp. 11,000,000	Rp. 8,100,000
4.	Singat River	Rp. 41,000,000	Rp. 12,000,000
5.	Putat River	Rp. 300,000	Rp. 250,000
6.	inang River Buring Slowan Kandis	Rp. 10,000,000	Rp. 2,000,000
7.	Pesunde River	Rp. 17,000,000	Rp. 9,100,000
8.	Selarai/ Pool Long	Rp. 4,200,000	Rp. 3,200,000
9.	RiverIlir Intersection	Rp. 10,100,000	Rp. 8,100,000
10.	Crossing	Rp. 8,600,000	Rp. 6,600,000

Source: processed by the author from the Report on the Implementation of Lebak Lebung Auction Activities in 4 Sub-districts in Sekayu District in 2024

In addition, of the 41 Lebak Lebung Auction Objects that were sold, there were some that experienced a price decrease, some of which can be seen in table 3 above, an increase in selling price, and so on, the proportions of which can be seen in table 4 below.

Table 4. Proportion of Lebak Lebung Auction Objects Based on Selling Price Sold in 2024

No	Type	Number of Auction Objects
1.	Decrease in selling price	18 Objects
2.	Improvement pricesell	8 Objects
3.	Price sell together withyear previously	10 Objects
4.	From No sold (2023)to be sold (2024)	3 Objects
5.	From sold (2023) to unsold (2024)	2 Objects

Source: processed by the author from the Report on the Implementation of Lebak Lebung Auction Activities in 4 Sub-districts in Sekayu District in 2024

In addition to the price decrease, there are also objects that experience price increases due to competition between buyers, especially land owners crossed by the Lebak Lebung, for example the Aneng-Aneng River which in 2023 was sold for Rp. 200,000,- to Rp. 3,500,000 in 2024. Regarding target group compliance, there are several reports from landowners around the Aneng-Aneng River that illegal levies by miners occurred in 2023 against landowners who inadvertently obstructed the river flow due to fallen trees, claiming the trees were damaging river biota. This illegal levies are certainly contrary to the Regent's Regulation and have caused unrest among surrounding landowners. From the data above, it can be concluded that miners as a target group have not fully complied with the policy. To anticipate these incidents, it is recommended that improvements be made, such as changing the initial bid percentage to be reduced or adding regulations regarding auction objects whose selling price was too high in the

previous year. Next, we will discuss the third dimension in policy implementation according to Smith (1973), namely the Implementing Organization.

c) Implementing Organization

According to Smith (1973), implementing organizations are the implementing agencies or government bureaucratic units responsible for implementing the policy. Indicators for this dimension include the organization's structure and personnel, leadership style and characteristics, and the general capacity of implementers within the organization. The first indicator is the organizational structure and personnel, namely employees at the Soak Baru Village Office as the host and organizer of the 2024 Lebak Lebung auction. Based on the Joint Decree of the Soak Baru Village Head, Balai Agung Village Head, Serasan Jaya Village Head and Kayuara Village Head Number 38 of 2024 concerning the Establishment of the Lebak Lebung and River Auction Implementation Committee in the Villages in Sekayu District, Musi Banyuasin Regency in 2024 - 2025 that:

- I. Coordinator : Head of Sekayu District
- II. Chief Executive: Head of Soak Baru Village
- III. Secretary: Secretary of Soak Baru Subdistrict
- IV. Member :
 1. Head of Government Affairs
 1. Head of Public Order and Public Order
 2. Head of LPM
 3. Treasurer

The committee composition above is in accordance with the provisions in Article 6 paragraph (5) of this Regent's Regulation. In addition to the Joint Decree of the Village Head, there is Decree of the Village Head of Soak Baru Number 37 of 2024 concerning the Lebak Lebung and River Auction Implementation Committee in Soak Baru, Balai Agung, Serasan Jaya and Kayuara Villages, Sekayu District, Musi Banyuasin Regency which regulates the division of members and tasks per section in the committee with a total of 19 people on the committee. Based on the author's observations, most of the committee members have carried out their duties per section, but there are several members who have not been active in carrying out their duties which causes imperfections in the implementation of the Lebak Lebung auction. In addition, the reduced committee composition compared to the previous year where in 2023 all treasurers and financial staff in 4 villages totaling 8 people became the auction committee to only the treasurer and financial staff of Soak Baru village totaling 4 people is one of the obstacles in calculating the cash deposited by the miners is not in line with the implementation of the event by the fast auction host. This causes long queues of miners to deposit money and the division of tasks that are not yet appropriate causes errors where the staff who receive the money deposit cannot hear the selling price that won the auction so that there is 1 miner who conveys a price below the bid that has been declared the winner by the host.

In addition, the preparation of administrative documents in the form of a Lebak Lebung Management Agreement, which should have been signed by the bidder, had to be completed two weeks after the auction was held due to the delay in the preparation of the Sekayu District Head's Decree concerning the Composition of the 2024 Lebak Lebung Auction Committee by the PPDK Section in Sekayu District. Based on the data, although the committee now consists of 19 people, there are still obstacles, especially in carrying out the duties of treasurer and recorder of auction object sales prices. Furthermore, the indicators of leadership style and nature in the organization, especially in Soak Baru Village, namely the Head of Soak Baru Village. His leadership nature is to give full trust to his subordinates. He is 57 years old and his work experience is from CPNS until 2023 from the Musi Banyuasin Regency Education Office for 28 years and the Musi Banyuasin Regency Social Service for 5 years who are accustomed to working with colleagues who are quite competent so they are accustomed to working with a system of being responsible independently for their respective duties and functions which underlies the leadership style. However, when applied in the Village Office environment with relatively low quality human resources, this leadership style is less appropriate because most of the subordinates in carrying out his duties really need active participation from superiors and some do not understand their duties and there are employees who do not want to carry out duties according to their positions. This leadership style and nature, along with the general capacity of its members, significantly influence the implementation of this policy. While the general capacity of the activity implementers is considered active, there are still individuals within the organization who fail to carry out their duties, impacting the organization's performance in the Lebak Lebung auction. Furthermore, the lack of attention and firmness from organizational leaders regarding sanctions against these individuals has contributed to the continued apathy of these individuals.

d) Environmental Factors

According to Smith (1973), the fourth dimension is environmental factors, which means elements in the environment that influence or are influenced by policy implementation, such as cultural, social, economic and political aspects. Culturally, there's a tradition where fishers are willing to offer high prices at auctions simply to maintain their pride, even if they incur losses because the fish won't reach the auction price. This culture undoubtedly drives higher auction prices and increases village revenues. On the social side, conflicts and disputes often arise between bidders and landowners surrounding auctioned properties, as mentioned in the case of Sungai Aneng-Aneng. These conflicts typically affect the auction price the following year, as both bidders and landowners attempt to outbid each other. This can also lead to higher auction prices. Furthermore, economic aspects also influence the implementation of the Lebak Lebung auction. The current difficult economic conditions have led to a decline in public interest in bidding on auction items due to the already high starting bids and the reduced fish catch, which has significantly impacted the community's ability to afford it. For example, Sungai Singat has seen its selling price drop significantly. Farfrom Rp. 41,000,000 to Rp. 12,000,000.

2. Factors Influencing the Implementation of Regent Regulation Number 72 of 2022 Concerning Procedures for Implementing Lebak Lebung Auctions in Villages/Sub-districts in Musi Banyuasin Regency in 4 Sub-districts in Sekayu District in 2024

The implementation of this Regent's Regulation is influenced by supporting and inhibiting factors which will be discussed as follows:

a) Supporting Factors

There are several supporting factors that support the implementation of this Regent's Regulation, namely:

1. The results of the Lebak Lebung auction are one of the original sources of income for the sub-district, so the higher the sales results of the auction object, the greater the funds managed by the sub-district government;
2. The Lebak Lebung auction will boost the economy of fishermen and fish processing communities. This will also lead to increased employment opportunities, especially for those processing the catch into smoked fish, bekasam, crackers, kemplang, and other traditional fish-based foods.
3. Establishing communication between fishermen, especially regarding fish catches, effective fishing methods and fish selling prices.

Apart from the supporting factors above, there are also inhibiting factors which will be explained as follows.

b) Inhibiting Factors

The inhibiting factors in the implementation of this Regent's Regulation are as follows:

1. The auction system causes high bidders who usually have strong capital to win the auction, so that fishermen with small capital do not have a chance.
2. Conflicts often occur between the land owners crossed by the auction object and the winning bidders.
3. Fishing using large tools such as funnels, tuguk, ponds and rakat Which endangering the sustainability of fish resources causes a decline in fish resources from year to year.
4. The initial offer amount of 75% of the previous year's selling price is less realistic because natural conditions are unpredictable and the fish catch does not always match the previous year and causes losses to fishermen.
5. There is cooperation between the bidders and other bidders so that the auction selling price decreases.
6. Obligations in conservation maintenance and maintaining environmental sustainability is often not done by enthusiasts
7. The auction winner usually determines the selling price of the fish, thus causing further losses to small fishermen.
8. Lack of attention from the relevant Regional Device Organizations regarding the auction proceeds has resulted in delays in their utilization.

c) Efforts to Overcome Inhibiting Factors

Efforts that can be made to overcome the inhibiting factors above are:

1. The Regional Government is paying attention to helping small farmers and fishermen to get financial injections in the form of loans from banks so they can compete in auctions.
2. Regulations regarding the limitation of the auction period need to be added so that surrounding land owners have the opportunity to win the auction.

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3. The agency tasked with supervising the Lebak Lebung auction must be active in supervising the management of auction objects.
4. It is necessary to add a point to the auction agreement letter to be willing to accept sanctions if they damage the fish ecosystem and other biota.
5. It is necessary to form fishing groups so that fishing activities are more sustainable.

CONCLUSION

The implementation of the Lebak Lebung auction in 4 sub-districts based on the Musi Banyuasin Regent Regulation Number 72 of 2022 concerning Procedures for Implementing the Lebak Lebung Auction in Villages/Sub-districts in Musi Banyuasin Regency has not been optimal because there are still several obstacles, namely the ineffective coordination and communication between policy makers and policy implementers, the community as investors have not fully complied with the contents of the policy, the quality of Human Resources in the implementing organization (Soak Baru Village Office) is still lacking, and frequent conflicts occur between investors and land owners crossed by the auction object. There are both supporting and inhibiting factors in the implementation of the Lebak Lebung auction. Supporting factors include the auction proceeds, which provide a source of revenue for the village government and create jobs for fishermen and fish processors. Meanwhile, inhibiting factors include the fact that investors generally own large amounts of capital, thus limiting opportunities for small-scale fishermen, the installation of large fishing gear that leads to a reduction in fish resources, and the lack of attention from relevant agencies regarding the financial management of Lebak Lebung auction proceeds.

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